

Speculation on Quantum Probabilities $W(x)$ (wavefunction) and $W^*(x)W(x)$

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Quantum mechanics utilizes a wavefunction $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ (in time independent cases) with $\exp(ipx)$ being what we call a free particle complex probability. In such a case, $W(x)$ is an OR scenario of these various probabilities. We have argued in previous notes that $\exp(ipx)$ is the probability for a p impulse hit at x , even if the center-of-mass of the particle is not at x . This means that impulse hits may occur probabilistically in space as in the 2-slit example which requires adding two probabilities as an OR case for each slit. The point then seems to be that $W(x)$ (or even its momentum frozen form $W^*(x)W(x)$) gives a profile in space of the number of interactions (various p impulse hits) at each x .

Classically, the kinetic energy (nonrelativistic) is $pp/2m$. In a classical bound problem this kinetic energy is considered to exist (in calculations) at the center-of-mass, but forces are also said to be rendered at this point so $pp/2m$, the center-of-mass and the force hit point all coincide. In quantum mechanics, a p impulse hit and the center-of-mass do not coincide. If p is said to hit at a probabilistic x , then it seems that $pp/2m$ should also be seen to exist at this same hit point. A physical interaction point verifies in a sense the location of $pp/2m$ in a probabilistic manner, i.e. $a(p) \exp(ipx)/W(x)$ is the probability used to calculate $KE_{average}$ and this is based on impulse hit locations. By normalizing using $W(x)$, one removes the relative number of average hits at each x and obtains a pure energy value at x . (This may then be used in a $KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E$ equation.)

On average $W(x)$ has zero points, which means that if one considers $W^*(x)W(x)$ to represent the motion-frozen-out spatial distribution of hits, then no hits are rendered at certain x points (on average). One might argue then that the particle cannot exist at x , but the center-of-mass can exist anywhere. One might next argue that there is no kinetic energy at x , but that cannot be true because $1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W$ has the same 0 points as W and the two divide. Thus, there is average kinetic energy at all bound points and this represents an average based on impulse hits ($\exp(ipx)$).

Classically, if one has many particles in a potential, one may write $\text{density}(x)V(x)$ to find the potential energy of the particles. This implies that the particles interact with $V(x)$, e.g. neutrinos usually do not interact. $\text{Density}(x)$ in a classical sense means that the center-of-mass and force hit point are both at x . In quantum mechanics, $\exp(ipx)$ represents the probability for a force hit point, $W(x)$ represents an average and $W^*(x)W(x)$ represents a motion-frozen average hit point. $W^*(x)W(x)V(x)$ seems to represent the average potential energy of the particle at x because $W^*(x)W(x)$ is linked with interaction. Even if a particle is not present, however, there is energy $V(x)$ in space. It seems that if $W^*(x)W(x) = 0$ at some x , then there is no average particle interaction at this point, but there is still average kinetic energy $\sum_p a(p) pp/2m \exp(ipx) / W(x)$ based on the probability for average probability hits. The key idea is that one normalizes probability by dividing by $W(x)$ in the average kinetic energy calculation. $W^*(x)W(x)$ is

normalized not at x , but integrating over dx and setting this value to 1. One has relative hit at x values represented by $W^*(x)W(x)$. For $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)=1$, each dx has the same average hit value (with one not being able to distinguish details in \hbar/p , i.e. this is a motion frozen result).

The question then becomes: Why would one write: $W^*(x)W(x) KE_{ave}(x)$? One might argue that this term occurs if one takes the quantum mechanical equation: $KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E_n$ and multiplies by $W^*(x)W(x)$. One may ask: Does $V(x)W^*(x)W(x)$ have physical meaning? $V(x)$ is the potential energy at x . The average interaction probability with $V(x)$ at x should be $W(x)V(x)$ and not $W^*(x)W(x)V(x)$. The latter is a classical mechanical idealization. If $W^*(x)W(x)$ is 3 at x_1 and 2 at x_2 , then it is as if the particle interacts 1.5 times more at x_1 and so if $V(x_1)=V(x_2)$, then this approach assumes 1.5 the interaction energy at x_1 . $KE_{ave}(x)$, however, is simply free particle energy (average) at x and one does not need to take this average value and multiply it by the relative number of interactions at x .

$W(x)$ has zero points meaning that there is no interaction at such a point on average. $KE_{ave}(x)$ on the other hand is the average energy at x based on the particle kinetic energy presence $pp/2m$ being at the point of an impulse hit. This does not mean that an interaction is occurring with $V(x)$ at this point in this formalism. Even a free particle has an $\exp(ipx)$ probability when it is not interacting. The sum $\sum \over p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ means that all of the interactions linked with x have occurred and one is making an OR calculation. $KE_{ave}(x)$ is free particle kinetic energy at x and $V(x)$ is potential energy (not interaction potential energy with the particle). Multiplying by $W^*(x)W(x)$ is a classical minded approach to creating a classical equation:

$$\text{density}(x) (KE_{ave}(x)+V(x)) = E \text{ density}(x) \quad ((1))$$

Here $KE_{ave}(x)$ would represent the average kinetic energy of a single particle and $\text{density}(x)$ would be the average number of particles at x . $\text{density}(x)KE(x)$ has a clear meaning. $W^*(x)W(x) KE_{ave}(x)$ on the other hand is different. $KE_{ave}(x)$ is actually the classical kinetic energy value at x and so it is not clear why one would multiply it by $W^*(x)W(x)$. $W^*(x)W(x)$ represents the probability for an impulse hit at x in a p -frozen out picture. The notion of $\exp(ipx)$ (i.e. probability for a p hit at x) is already buried within the quantum calculation of $KE_{ave}(x)$ (which yields the classical value). In order to find the physical meaning of $W^*(x)W(x)$ multiplied by $KE_{ave}(x)$ or $V(x)$ it seems that one has broken dx into equally sized segments which correspond to different detection hits of the particle. This is then somehow equated with the presence of the particle per unit time in dx which is then somehow rendered as the average energy at x multiplied by the detected presence at x through a steady rate of measurement/time. Thus, multiplying by $W^*(x)W(x)$ is not multiplying by a physical density.

The Meaning of $W(x)$

Quantum mechanical calculations deal with the free particle probability $\exp(ipx)$ which we argue represents the probability to have a p impulse hit at x , even if the center-of-mass of the particle is not at x .

$$W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx) \quad ((2))$$

$W(x)$ is an OR situation probability which represents the probability of any p hit at x . It is $W(x)$ which is obtained in time-independent calculations. $W(x)$ may have zeros which would imply no average probability to interact at x . Furthermore, classical values like $pp/2m$ which still hold for any free particle in quantum mechanics are averaged using $\exp(ipx)$, e.g.

$$KE_{ave}(x) = \{\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)pp/2m \exp(ipx)\} / W(x) \quad ((3))$$

((3)) represents a pure kinetic energy value at x because the probability is normalized by dividing by $W(x)$. In other words, if $W(x)$ has zero points, then the numerator of ((3)) has zero points at the exact same points because:

$$KE_{ave}(x) = E - V(x) \quad ((4))$$

This begs the question: How does one interpret $\exp(ipx)$ fully?

We argued that $\exp(ipx)$ represents the probability to have a p impulse hit at x . $\exp(ipx)$, however, represents a particle with constant speed which spends the same amount of time in each dx . This mention of time is key, we argue, because it means that even with the $\exp(ipx)$ form, one considers equal dx units and also equal measurement probes in time which try to interact with $\exp(ipx)$ without involving $\hbar/p = \Delta x$ resolution. Thus the ideas of $W^*(x)W(x)$ are already found in $W(x)$. The constant modulus of $\exp(ipx)$ is directly linked with $W^*(x)W(x)=1$ and the same number of time hits (constant rate of measurement probe) for each dx . The unnormalized form $W^*(x)$ or $W^*(x)W(x)$ means that one is considering hits in time (in a classical view, actually $W^*(x)W(x)$ is the average number of interactions at x) with equally spaced dx . When one normalizes using $W(x)$ in the denominator, one removes all time considerations and so only has energy in x as in the calculation of $KE(x)$. Regardless of the fact that $\exp(ipx)$ represents the probability for a p hit at x and is linked with equal time (rate) measurement probes, there is still kinetic energy at x . If one is only interested in energy at x , then $W^*(x)W(x)$ is of no consequence and one solves a strict energy equation:

$$KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = KE_{ave}(x) = \{\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)pp/2m \exp(ipx)\} / W(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((5))$$

$W(x)$ and E arise as solutions if $W(x)$ is set to 0 at \pm infinite.

As a result, multiplying ((5)) by $W^*(x)W(x)$ is really taking the energy at x (within dx) and multiplying it by the number of equal time (rate) probe hits in dx . This has the appearance of a density(x), but is completely different. One views three time hits in dx_1 versus two time hits in

dx^2 as meaning that there is 1.5 more time energy at dx_1 in time (if $KE_{ave}(x_1)=KE_{ave}(x_2)$). If one only considers space, then the average energy is simply $KE_{ave}(x)$ and the time spent in dx or the more accurately $W^*(x)W(x)$, the probability to interact is irrelevant. The interaction feature has already been considered by using $\exp(ipx)$ to calculate $KE_{ave}(x)$. The notion of time is a classical one. Quantum mechanically, $W^*(x)W(x)$ represents the number of interactions at x_1, dx versus x_2, dx , but we argue that this has nothing to do with the energy at (x_1, x_2) . In other words, $W^*(x)W(x)$ is the measuring person's biased view that more hits means more particles.

Different Normalizations of $a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$ and $W^*(x)W(x)$

Both $a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$ and $W^*(x)W(x)$ are normalized probabilities, but they are normalized very differently. $W^*(x)W(x)$ is normalized at each x (integral over x) Giving relative x probe hit successes at each x (within dx). $a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$ is normalized at a given x point and yields the probability for a p hit at x . Overall, it removes the average number of hits at x by dividing by $W(x)$.

Consequence of Multiplying by $W^*(x)W(x)$

$KE_{ave}(x)$ is the kinetic energy average due to probability $\exp(ipx)$ at x to have a p hit. It contains a set of $\exp(ipx)$ s. $W^*(x)W(x)$ happens to be the correct math factor to convert $KE_{ave}(x)$, when integrating over dx to

$$\text{Sum over } p \quad p^2/2m \int a(p)a(p) dx = KE \text{ total} \quad ((6))$$

Formally, one might call

$$W^*(x)W(x) = P(x) \quad ((7a)) \quad \text{and} \quad a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x) = P(p/x) \quad ((7))$$

We argue, however, that this is a formalism. The basic idea seems to be that for

$$W^*(x)W(x)V(x) \quad ((8))$$

If one has 3 interactions at x_1 versus 2, at x_2 , then there are 1.5 times the interactions at x_1 with an energy $V(x)$ present. Thus, $W^*(x)W(x)V(x)$ enhances (by multiplication) the energy by the number interaction tries. Strictly speaking, however, energy at x is not increased by more interaction tries, but the interaction energy of the particle might be said to increase.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that one needs to know how to interpret $W(x)$, $W^*(x)W(x)$ and $a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$. We suggest that both $W(x)$ and $W^*(x)W(x)$, the latter being normalized over dx to 1 represent the number of average interactions by the particle with say $V(x)$ at x . This seems to be interpreted as extra interaction of the particle $W^*(x)W(x)V(x)$. In space, however, one has energy $V(x)$ based on the potential, even if there are no interactions. If one uses an

average of $\exp(ipx)$ s, model to calculate kinetic energy, then one may create the average $\{\text{Sum over } p \frac{a(p)\exp(ipx) p^2/2m}{W(x)}\}$ at x . The normalization by $W(x)$ removes in a sense the number of interactions at x , leaving simply the pure energy which is used in a conservation law. Multiplying $\text{KEave}(x)$ by $W^*(x)W(x)$ mathematically isolates the various $p^2/2m$ values and gives them weights of $a(p)a(p)$ which is the momentum probability. $\exp(ipx)$, on the other hand, is the probability for a particle with p to hit at x .